

ORIGINAL PAPER

Efficacy of homeopathic treatment of skin reactions during radiotherapy for breast cancer: a randomised, double-blind clinical trial

A Balzarini¹*, E Felisi², A Martini³ and F De Conno¹

¹Rehabilitation and Palliative Care Department, National Cancer Institute, Milan; ²Centro Italiano di Studi e di Documentazione in Omeopatia, Milan; and ³Biomedical Advisers C.R.O, Milan

The aim of this study was to assess the effects of *Belladonna* 7cH and X-ray 15cH associated in the treatment of acute radiodermatitis. A randomized double-blind placebo-controlled clinical trial involving 66 patients who had been operated on for breast cancer and were undergoing radiotherapy was conducted. The following parameters were assessed over ten weeks: breast skin colour, warmth, swelling and pigmentation.

The efficacy of the treatment was assessed by the comparison of these parameters taken individually and by calculating an Index of Total Severity (sum of the scores of the four parameters) during radiotherapy, and during recovery, 15 and 30 d after the end of the radiotherapy.

The differences of the scores of the Index of Total Severity during Radiotherapy were not statistically significant, but showed a trend towards a better activity of the homeopathic medicine compared to placebo. Analysis of the data on Total Severity during recovery, showed a statistically significant benefit of the active medicines over placebo. The homeopathic medicines had particular effectiveness on the heat of the skin.

The limited number of patients observed and the posology employed could have interfered with the significance of the results. Chemotherapy and hormonotherapy do not seem to affect the results. *British Homeopathic Journal* (2000) 89, 8–12.

Keywords: breast cancer; radiotherapy; *Belladonna*; Xray

Introduction

Women operated on for breast cancer usually undergo radiotherapy associated with systemic therapies (chemotherapy and/or hormonotherapy) after surgery.¹

In conservative surgery (quadrantectomy with axillary dissection), radiotherapy (lasting 6 weeks) is carried out using cobalt-therapy on the residual mammary parenchyma at the dose of 50 Gy and with roengentherapy on the scar at the dose of 10 Gy.

During treatment, local and general side effects (skin reactions, asthenia and rarely nausea) the intensity of which depends on: the accumulated dose; the type of employed radiation; and the patient's sensibility.

The cutaneous picture consists of radiodermatitis. This clinical condition is manifest in almost every irradiated patient, (90% of cases) causing discomfort and is generally regarded as the most troublesome problem in radiotherapy. The most frequent and constant initial lesion is erythema, which, in some cases, can be ingravescens, lead to dry exfoliation and then to humid desquamation and finally to ulceration and necrosis.^{2–5}

The repair process often causes cutaneous and subcutaneous fibrosis, with teleangiectasias which

*Correspondence: Dr A Balzarini, Rehabilitation and Palliative Care Department, National Cancer Institute, via Venezian 1, Milan, Italy.

appear months or even years after the radiotherapy. Hyperpigmentation is very frequent.⁶

Intense hyperaemia and radiant heat associated with slight oedema are characteristic of this kind of erythema. This anatomic and pathological picture coincides with the clinical picture of cutaneous inflammation caused by intoxication with *Belladonna*, a solanaceous plant commonly employed in homeopathy.^{7,8}

Homeopathy is a therapeutic method based on the law of similars which treats a clinical picture with a substance capable of producing the same clinical picture in a healthy patient.⁹⁻¹¹

Radiodermatitis presents such a precise causality as to justify the use of an aetiological remedy in the homeopathic therapeutical pattern.¹²

The aim of this trial is to assess the efficacy and a new indication of *Belladonna* in radiodermatitis and to analyze the synergistic action of a symptomatic remedy (*Belladonna*) and an etiological one (*X-ray*).

Method

A sample of 66 patients was recruited sequentially and informed consent obtained. All had undergone conservative surgery for breast cancer and were being treated with radiotherapy (QU.A.R.T: quadrantectomy with axillary dissection and radiotherapy).

Patients who lived too far from the hospital and those who had severe associated diseases at the time of the trial (diabetes mellitus and systemic skin diseases) were excluded.

The study was conducted according to a randomized two-parallel groups design carried out under double-blind conditions vs placebo.¹³ The granules were taken sublingually.

Both groups used a topical medication containing fluocortolone, generally prescribed at the beginning of the radiotherapy.

The homeopathic treatment consisted of *Belladonna* 7cH, 3 granules sublingually twice a day and *X-ray* 15cH, 3 granules sublingually once a day.¹⁴ *X-ray* 15 cH was obtained with progressive solutions-succussions of a water-alcohol solution irradiated with X-rays up to a concentration of 10⁻³⁰. The solution was exposed for 25 min at 10 Gray, 150 Kvolts, 10mA, without filtration; the irradiation field was 8cm×10cm and the distance from the irradiation source was 40 cm. The dose was calculated with the aid of dosimetry in ionization chamber. The drugs and the placebo employed in this trial were provided by Laboratoires Boiron, Lyon (France).

The patients were checked weekly during the 6-week radiotherapy and 15 and 30 d after its end (recovery).

At every observation we evaluated (table 1):

- the skin colour, employing a scale of chromatic tonalities (normal = 0, pink = 1, red-violet = 2);

Table 1 Scores: Patients number: placebo 32, verum 29

Parameter	Score
Oedema	no = 0
	yes = 1
Hyperpigmentation	no = 0
	yes = 1
Heat	no = 0
	faint = 1
	intense = 2
Colour	normal = 0
	pink = 1
	red-violet = 2

- heat to the touch, assessed by means of a numerical scale from 0 (normal temperature) to 2 (intense heat);
- cutaneous and/or subcutaneous oedema (absent = 0, present = 1);
- cutaneous hyperpigmentation (absent = 0, present = 1).

Every patient's data were collected on a special card compiled by the same doctor to avoid differences of assessment. Two doctors were involved in the assessment of the whole sample.

The procedures followed were in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 1983, informed consent was obtained from every patient.

Statistical analysis

The homogeneity of the two groups at baseline was tested by means of a one-way analysis of variance (equivalent to Student's *t*-test for independent samples) for data on interval scale (age), and with the χ^2 test (and/or indexes equivalent to it) for nominal data expressed in form of frequency (incidence of chemotherapy).

The efficacy of the treatment was assessed by comparison, for each of the chosen parameters, of the frequency (data expressed on nominal scale: oedema and hyperpigmentation) or the severity (data expressed on ordinal scale: colour and heat) in the two groups at every observation. This was assessed by chi-square test (frequency) and Mann-Whitney U-test (severity).

By summing the scores regarding the severity of the four parameters at each observation for every patient, we obtained the Index of Total Severity during Radiotherapy (TSI) (concerning the six observations the patients underwent during therapy) and the Index of Total Severity during Recovery (RTSI) (concerning the two observations which took place respectively 15 and 30 d after the end of the radiotherapy). These indices are composed of parameters which were assessed by means of different scales: for oedema and hyperpigmentation, a nominal scale ranging from 0 to 1; for colour and heat, a ordinal scale ranging from 0 to 2. The colour and heat parameters have

therefore a greater weight, but since the indices were created to globalise the comparison between the two groups, the different weight of the parameters does not impair the comparison because they are symmetrically represented in the two groups. The significance of the difference of the two indices in the two groups, was assessed by means of a parametric test (one-way analysis of variance). For all our comparisons we arbitrarily fixed the limit of statistic significance at $P < 0.05$ (two-tailed).

The risk of accumulative type I error in multiple comparison tests was accounted for by means of Bonferroni correction.

Results

Sixty-one patients of 66 were assessed at follow-up ten weeks after the beginning of the therapy (8th observation); there were four dropouts due to adverse effects of radiation (mostly epigastralgia) at the second week of treatment and one because of homeopathic exacerbation. All patients had taken the remedies regularly.

The mean age of the patients was 52.7 with a minimum of 28.3 and a maximum of 70. No patients had local cutaneous lesions at the time of recruitment. Two patients had reported urticaria in their anamnesis, one suffered from psoriasis of the hands and another one from mycosis of the back.

On opening the envelopes containing the randomisation code we discovered that 29 patients had been administered the verum (group V) and 32 the placebo (group P).

No statistically significant differences were observed concerning age (51.7 and 53.8 years in group V and in group P respectively, $P=0.48$), post-surgery damage (73.3% in the homeopathically treated patients and 68.7% in placebo patients) and other therapies (in both groups 8 patients were undergoing chemotherapy: 25% in group P and 27% in group V). The side effects were equally distributed between the two groups.

We regarded the following parameters as the most significant: the colour of the skin, the intensity of the heat, the oedema and the hyperpigmentation. (Table 1) We noticed that the frequency of oedema was higher in the group treated with the active remedies at all observations except the second. The difference between the two groups of treatment reached statistical significance at the fifth and sixth week (41% of frequency of oedema in the group treated with homeopathic remedies and 16% in the group treated with placebo) (Table 2).

Hyperpigmentation had a favourable trend for active remedies which reached statistical significance at the fifth week and was near significance at the eighth observation (Table 3).

Erythema was of the same severity and frequency in the two groups. In the group treated with the active

Table 2 Frequency of the oedema during the 8 weeks of observation (%)

Observation	Verum frequency	Placebo frequency	Pearson test P-value
1	13.8	6.3	0.320
2	10.3	12.5	0.790
3	17.2	15.6	0.360
4	31.0	18.8	0.260
5	41.4	15.6	0.025
6	41.4	15.6	0.025
7	27.6	12.5	0.140
8	10.3	9.4	0.890

Table 3 Frequency of hyperpigmentation during the 8 weeks of observation (%)

Observation	Verum frequency	Placebo frequency	Pearson test P-value
1	0	0	
2	0	0	
3	3.4	0	0.290
4	6.9	9.4	0.720
5	6.9	25	0.050
6	24.1	34.4	0.380
7	58.6	56.3	0.850
8	24.1	46.9	0.060

remedies, the recovery appeared more round (Table 4). At every observation the increasing of the heat of the skin to the touch was less marked in the patients treated with homeopathy. The difference in favour of homeopathy became statistically significant at the third observation and it remained such until the first observation after the end of the radiotherapy, except the fifth (Table 5). At the final observation, the

Table 4 Average of color score during the 8 weeks of observation

Observation	Verum average score	Placebo average score	Mann-Whitney test P-value
1	0.482	0.406	0.550
2	0.655	0.656	0.990
3	0.758	0.750	0.890
4	0.827	0.843	0.960
5	1.000	1.062	0.690
6	1.103	1.125	0.840
7	0.724	0.781	0.790
8	0.276	0.406	0.280

Table 5 Average of heat score during the 8 weeks of observation

Observation	Verum average score	Placebo average score	Mann-Whitney test P-value
1	0.000	0.062	0.340
2	0.000	0.187	0.090
3	0.000	0.375	0.008
4	0.103	0.562	0.016
5	0.310	0.718	0.116
6	0.241	0.781	0.023
7	0.069	0.562	0.011
8	0.069	0.250	0.250

advantage of the verum over placebo was no longer significant.

The analysis of the data on the total severity during radiotherapy and during recovery has shown an advantage of the active remedies over the placebo. This advantage was statistically significant at the analysis of variance for the Index of Total Severity during Recovery (RTSI): the average score was 2.345 for the verum and 3.250 for the placebo ($P=0.05$) (Table 6). The differences of the scores of the Index of Total Severity during Radiotherapy (TTSI) (7.448 and 9.062 for the verum and the placebo respectively) were not statistically significant ($P=0.23$), but they appear to reveal a better activity of the homeopathic remedies vs placebo (Table 7).

Discussion

The indication for the therapeutic use of *Belladonna* in severe radiodermatitis is based on anatomo-pathological similarity between the clinical picture of the latter and the pathogenetic picture of the cutaneous phlogosis of the remedy. In fact both present as main features: intense hyperaemia, radiant heat, oedema and variable pain.

In homeopathy causality is generally one of the most important elements when choosing the medicine, although its verification often proves difficult because it is seldom possible to recognize a clear cause-effect connections between a particular event and the pathology.

This connection is manifest and unquestionable in the case of acute radiodermatitis; we considered it logical to study the possible therapeutical synergism between *Belladonna*, as a symptomatic remedy and *X-rays*, as an etiological remedy. Our results gave partial confirmation to the hypotheses we wanted to check at the beginning of the trial.

Although the comparison among the average scores of the Total Severity during radiotherapy (TTSI) shows an advantage of the remedies over the placebo, no statistically significant differences were noticed. On the other hand the comparison of the average

scores of the total gravity indexes during recovery (RTSI) proved to be significant ($P=0.05$).

On analysing the four parameters separately we have:

- 1 *Belladonna* does not have therapeutic effects on oedema (we believe that the statistically significant differences noticed in the favour of the placebo were random); this is in accordance with the law of similarity because oedema has minor importance in the pathogenetic picture of the remedy.
- 2 The results concerning the changes of the colour and the heat of the irradiated skin seem to show that the remedies affect mainly the hyperaemia of the deep strata of the skin. In fact the differences concerning the colour of the skin in the two groups were not significant, while the heat changed in a significant way during most of the period of observation.
- 3 The results concerning hyperpigmentation show an advantage of the active medicines over the placebo, especially during recovery ($P=0.06$), in accordance with the fact that such lesion usually appears late during radiodermatitis.

At this moment we do not have enough data to support the possible preventive effect of the remedies on post-radiotherapy cutaneous fibrosis. The possible interference of chemo and hormonotherapy on the reduced therapeutic response was analysed, but no statistically significant differences were observed between the two groups.

The posological regime may require revision. In fact the association of *Belladonna* and *X-rays* has required a less frequent administration of *Belladonna* than it is indicated by its pharmacokinetics of acute illnesses. A case of homeopathic aggravation was noticed too; a patient suffering from menopausal syndrome before the beginning of the treatment showed a worsening in the intensity of her symptoms (hot flushes, perspiration and migraine) and had to stop the remedy.

Conclusions

Our observations on the response to *Belladonna* 7cH and *X-ray* 15cH in the treatment of acute radiodermatitis indicate that the best therapeutic efficacy is noted when hyperaemia is more striking and oedema is less severe.

We consider that further research in the field is justified, particularly concerning the use of *Belladonna* in association with another symptomatic medicine in order to achieve a wider anatomopathological simile, the increase of the administration frequency and of the number of granules per administration and the assessment of the late local post-actinic outcome (subcutaneous thickening and reduced skin elasticity).

Table 6 Index of Total Severity during radiotherapy (TTSI) 1–6 weeks

	Average of total score	s.d.	One-way Anova P-value
Verum	7.448	3.439	0.23
Placebo	9.062	6.47	

Table 7 Index of Total Severity during recovery (RTSI) 7–8 weeks

	Average of total score	s.d.	One-way Anova P-value
Verum	2.345	1.343	0.05
Placebo	3.250	2.079	

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